

AMPERE: An European project aimed to decrease the Levelized Cost of Energy with innovative heterojunction bifacial module solution ready for the market.

Battaglia A.⁽¹⁾; Gerardi C.⁽²⁾; Scali S.⁽²⁾; Bizzarri F.⁽²⁾; Strahm B.⁽³⁾; Soederstroem T.⁽⁴⁾; Munoz D.⁽⁵⁾; Ribeyron P.-J.⁽⁵⁾; Izzi M.⁽⁶⁾; Tucci M.⁽⁶⁾; Delli Veneri P.⁽⁶⁾; Despeisse M.⁽⁷⁾; Perret-Aebi L.⁽⁷⁾; Ballif C.⁽⁷⁾; Nielsen O.⁽⁸⁾; Hartlin B.⁽⁹⁾; Aquino C.⁽⁹⁾; Zink O.⁽¹⁰⁾; Melzer B.⁽¹⁰⁾; Tallian M.⁽¹¹⁾; Lombardo S.⁽¹²⁾; Balucani M.⁽¹³⁾; Rentsch. J.⁽¹⁴⁾

- 1) 3SUN, Contrada Blocco Torrazze Zona Industriale 95121, Catania, Italy, 2) EGP-Enel Green Power Viale Regina Margherita 125, 00198 Roma, Italy, 3) MBR-Meyer Burger Research, Rouges Terres 61, 2068 Hauterive Switzerland, 4) MBS-Meyer Burger AG, Schorenstrasse 39, CH-3645 Gwatt (Thun) Switzerland, 5) CEA-LITEN, Institut National de l'Energie Solaire (INES), Savoie Technolac, F-73375 Le Bourget du Lac, France, 6) ENEA Research Center, Via Anguillarese 301, 00123 Roma, 7) CSEM, PV-center, Jaquet Droz-1, 2000 Neuchâtel, Switzerland, 8) Norway NorSun AS, Karenslyst Allé 9C, NO-0278 OSLO, Norway, 9) ERM, Saint Mary Axe 33, EC3A 8AA London, United Kingdom, 10) J&R-Jonas & Redmann Automationstechnik GmbH, Kaiserin-Augusta-Allee 113, 10553 Berlin, Germany, 11) Semilab Co. Ltd., Prielle Kornélia u.2., 1117 Budapest, Hungary, 12) CNR, Istituto per la Microelettronica e Microsistemi (IMM) Zona Industriale, Ottava Strada, 5, 95121, Catania, Italy, 13) RISE Technology, 18 Via Monte Bianco, San Martino di Lupari – PD, 35018 Italy, 13) F-ISE, Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems (ISE), Heidenhofstrasse 2, 79110 Freiburg, Germany

Abstract — AMPERE project aims to the setting-up of an innovative 100 MWp/y full-scale automated pilot line delivering a power module of 390 Wp based on an industrial heterojunction solution with a bifacial architecture (G/G 72-cells). A rapid scale up to 240 MWp/y is planned and a pathway towards the GWp/y factory defined. The implementation of the heterojunction technologies into these industrial manufacturing lines will demonstrate that the production of PV products at a remarkable decrease of LCOE is possible. The project will target an LCOE reduction of at least 15% compared to mainstream PV mc-Si technology.

I. INTRODUCTION

Solar energy is expected to be an integral technology in the creation of a low-carbon future. The Levelized Cost of Energy, LCOE is today the metric largely used by PV sector to quantify electricity generation costs. The LCOE is defined as the average generation cost, i.e., including all the costs involved in supplying PV at the point of connection to the grid. As solar players push to increase their market share, the competition with conventional technologies intensifies. Hence, PV electricity production not only seeks to reach parity with conventional generation sources, but aims to even surpass them on an LCOE basis to compensate for its intermittent nature. A race towards lower costs and higher competitiveness in PV sector has led to a readily decrease of module prices over time as the historical PV Learning Curve teaches. LCOE

reduction, among the other important factors, is influenced from the high efficiency of cell and power output of the module. Since the global market for very high efficiency cells is still limited but rapidly expanding growing and building up of new capacities in Europe for high efficiency technology based on high innovation such as industrial heterojunction, might be achieved rapidly[1].

AMPERE, acronym for Automated photovoltaic cell and Module industrial Production to regain and secure European Renewable Energy market, aims to establish the next generation PV technology with cell efficiencies of 23% and 390Wp module power at production level in a 100MWp/y pilot line production; an improvement in efficiency will be achieved in the subsequent development of the line to 250 MWp/y soon after the end of project, targeting an average cell efficiency of more than 23.5% and a module output power more than 400Wp. In the contest of the PV high efficiency innovation AMPERE project aims to assure the full value chain sustainability in modules and cells production, with very high quality, high innovation rates, large scale manufacturing and a certain extent of vertical integration for reaching and maintaining a globally competitive position.

Moreover the bifacial solar cells and modules architectures are more than a promising approach to increase the energy output of photovoltaic systems and consequently the LCOE due to its less footprint and manpower due to fewer process

steps, efficiency potential up to 26%, bifacial with backside improvement in terms of energy/our and a lower temperature coefficient[2]. Such characteristic will reduce the overall levelised cost of energy to a level competitive with that of the actual mainstream industrial PV technologies multi-crystalline BSF and PERC.

The bifacial heterojunction technology will be scaled up to a more mature industrial level for mass production. The project will be focused on the improvement of PV module power, reliability and durability to reduce the cost needed to fix and maintain PV plant and decrease its operational risks. The metric will be applied on the existing PV module thin film industrial production site of 3SUN (owned by Enel Green Power) in Catania, Italy.

II. AMPERE OBJECTIVES

Silicon heterojunction solar cells can achieve efficiencies more than 26 % as Kaneka has showed recently[3]. However, most of these record cells have been achieved at the R&D scale and even if on mass production several company are working (Panasonic firstly) their production capacity are limited actually mainly due to difficulties in developing high efficiency solar cell industrial production from a site, as well as to high capital cost to build SHJ production line from the other[4].

AMPERE starts from existing technologies platforms in the field of the heterojunction technologies that have been largely demonstrated their effectiveness worldwide, namely the Cells Technological Platform of CEA-INES [5] and the Cell and Module Technological Platform of Mayer Burger [6]. They are the hard base of the project, where a technology selection process will enable the implementation of the best materials and instruments into the existing industrial production line of 3SUN [7], which will work as demonstration bed to reach the AMPERE objectives of 23% cell efficiencies and more than 390Wp module power at production level in a high automated and highly innovative 100MWp/y pilot line production and a 15% LCOE reduction.

The end-user of the project is Enel Green Power [8] a leader in the renewable energy production sector operating worldwide. The project operate along with the support of high level European research institutes (CSEM, EPFL, F-ISE, ENEA, CNR) as well as key EU companies covering the whole PV value chain (Norsun, Rise technology, Jonas & Redmann, ERM).

The project will target an LCOE reduction of at least 15% compared to conventional PV mc-Si technology.

AMPERE project promise to be competitive with the Premium Market consisting of PERC, IBC and current HJT. AMPERE performance assessment in terms of LCOE is presented in figure1.

Fig. 1. Ampere cells and modules technology expected positioning in terms of LCOE (€/cent/KWh) compared with premium PV market.

Key aspects for European PV market, to compete with mainstream providers, pass through fundamental steps that embrace technological and marketing aspects that AMPERE will purchase, such as:

- ✓ Improve performances without affecting the process complexity to maintain the CAPEX at a limited level
- ✓ Improve reliability towards 40 years lifetime for better LCOE
- ✓ Use of abundant, non-toxic materials
- ✓ Recyclable and low footprint technology
- ✓ Increase market need for the technology
- ✓ GWp factory perspective

III. AMPERE OUTCOMES

Among the existing solar cells technologies, HJT has demonstrated a large potential to address the above mentioned challenges. Furthermore, the HJT solar module can be fabricated in a bi-facial architecture, further enhancing the electricity production capacity by at least 20% and opening up many market segments[1].

A first breakdown of costs and a draft of industrial plan has been analyzed and settled. It comes especially from the high level of automation and process control inside the innovation transfer that allow a global cost reduction around 30%. Many other factors and technological aspects has been analyzed. The expected cost reduction within AMPERE in its PV value chain comes firstly from the levels represented in subsequent table 1.

As the share of different PV technology approaching the market increases, it is logical to compare electricity generation by the different PV technology sources and calculate the energy price by means of the LCOE: this allows different technologies to be compared on the basis of a simple common data input.

TABLE I
Ampere project main cost reduction expected

	Objective within AMPERE	Cost reduction
At wafer level	Thinner wafers	~25%
At cell level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Lower Silver content · Cheaper TCO · Use of Cu for metallization 	~40%
At module level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Replace Indium in wires · Develop 72 cells · Develop half cells 	~30%
At process level	Lower CAPEX for production (PVD, PECVD) of cells and SWCT (module)	~20%
Global reduction	-	~30%

To show the potential of new industrial AMPERE technologies a preliminary evaluation to compare the mainstream and PERC premium technologies with the bifacial heterojunction cell at 23% efficiency expected in the project, in terms of Energy Yield (KWh/KWp) and the corresponding LCOE (\$cent/KWp) has been made. The results are summarized in the subsequent figure. The change €/€ has been taken to 1,222.

Fig. 3. Ampere LCOE (\$cent/KWh) compared with mainstream.

The main assumption under the estimation done are: 2000 KW/m² yearly irradiation (optimal for south of Italy), 55 °C module work temperature, 1.5% LID for PERC and for HJ 20% albedo effect and 35 years lifetime system. AMPERE project route will start by modifying and upgrading the pre-existing 3-SUN Thin Film silicon PV production line in such a way to reduce CAPEX. The project will follow two complementary routes during its three years of project. They include the acquisition and installation of new equipment for the manufacturing of HJT bifacial modules and the reuse of part of actual Thin Film production line.

IV. AMPERE IMPLEMENTATIONS

The outcomes of AMPERE Project will be used by 3SUN to implement extended automation for higher volume manufacturing to 250MWp/y, allowing to significantly reduce the final manufacturing costs. The fully automated 250MWp/y will enable Enel Green Power to break into the utility scale market with an innovative and robust technology PV solution. AMPERE project will deliver the roadmap to reach 1 GW production capacity. Increasing to 1GWp scale will reduce the costs. 3SUN has estimated a budgetary cost well under 0.4\$/Wp for the Gigawatt factory in which their already existing facilities can work as leverage. There is obviously room for implementations with the prospect of achieving further reductions in LCOE values of 25%; this will be achieved through savings all along the value chain and also as the result of future economies of scale.

V. CONCLUSIONS

A premium technology with high efficiency, high reliability, low temperature coefficient and consequently low LCOE will be industrialized in Europe, through the AMPERE project. The aim of AMPERE is to demonstrate innovative and sustainable manufacturing of bifacial heterojunction modules in a pilot line capable of manufacturing up to 100MW/y. These expected outcomes will be assessed and evaluated as a solid milestone for the viability of a 250 MWp/y production scale factory in 2020. AMPERE will provide investment pathways for the exploitation of the results to support the GW factory of the next 5-10 years. The project will be developed in the pre-existing thin film production line of the company 3SUN located in Catania, Italy.

ACKNOWLEDGE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon2020 Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under Grant Agreement N° 745601.

REFERENCES

- [1] *International Technology Roadmap for Photovoltaic (ITRPV). Seventh edition: march 2017*, p.54
- [2] F. Fertig, S. Nold, N. Wöhrle, J. Greulich et al., "Economic feasibility of bifacial silicon solar cells," *Prog. Photovolt: Res. Appl.* Vol 24, pp. 800-817, 2016.
- [3] K. Yoshikawa, H. Kawasaki, W. Yoshida, T. Irie, et al., *Nature Energy*, vol 2, Issue 5, pp. 17032-1738, 2017.
- [4] *Global Market Outlook, Solar Power / 2015 – 2019*, p.54.
- [5] <http://liten.cea.fr/cea-tech/liten/en>
- [6] <http://www.meyerburger.com/en/products-systems/industries/photovoltaics/>
- [7] <http://www.3sun.com/>
- [8] <https://www.enelgreenpower.com/>